

Sighting of Greater White Fronted Goose in Hadinaru Kere, Mysore

Shiva Kumar Basavaraj¹, Raj Kumar Devaraje Urs² and T. S. Harsha³

²Wildlife Conservation Foundation, 177, Hebbal industrial area, Phase-1, Mysore. 570 018,

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Environmental Science, Karnataka State Open University, Mysore-570006, Karnataka State

Abstract:- Regular birding visit was carried out to Hadinaru lake, in the taluk of Nanjangud, Mysuru district. During bird watching, it was noticed the huge congregation of Bar-Headed Goose *Anser indicus*. One of the authors was also observed an *Anser* species similar to *Grey lag Goose* as the birds had put its neck the other side, after spending more time and keenly observing the bird a white patch above the pinkish beak was strongly prominent, though the yellow ring wasn't properly visible once photographed the bird was easily distinguished. The present observation also stands to be the farthest inland record of the bird in the Indian Subcontinent.

I. INTRODUCTION

White Fronted goose, also called Speckle belly, or Laughing Goose, (species *Anser albifrons*), rather small, dark-bodied goose with white forehead, yellow bill, and irregular black patches on the belly; it is classified in the tribe Anserini of the family Anatidae (order Anseriformes). Breeding in the Arctic, the white-fronted goose, which exists in four or five races, is the most widely distributed of the so-called gray geese (*see* goose). It migrates as far south as Mexico, the Mediterranean Sea, India, and Japan. The European white-fronted goose (*Anser a. albifrons*) winters in western Europe, the British Isles, and Central Asia. The largest form, the tule goose (*A. a. gambelli*), winters only in the Sacramento Valley, California.

II. STUDY AREA

Fig. 1. Map showing Hadinaru lake: (Latitude: 12.166693 N; Longitude: 76.739426 E)

Hadinaru Lake in Nanjangud taluk is a favourite among the Bar-Headed Geese (Fig.1). The tank bund road takes you to the village Hadinaru, a mid-sized village hamlet in southern India surrounded by paddy fields irrigated by the Kabini river canals that criss-cross the surrounding paddy fields. Thus inviting the migratory goose species that night feed on the paddy shoots available plenty after harvested. Polluted due to pesticide inlet by paddy fields, Hadinaru village also drains its output into the gradient lake, observed people washing clothes and using the lake for fishing.

III. OBSERVATION

On February 10th 2023, the author on his regular birding visit to Hadinaru lake, in the taluk of Nanjangud, Mysuru district. While watching the huge congregation of Bar-Headed Goose *Anser indicus*, One of the Author (SKB) saw an *Anser* species similar to *Grey lag Goose* as the birds had put its neck the other side (Fig. 2), after spending more time and keenly observing the bird a white patch above the pinkish beak was strongly prominent, though the yellow ring wasn't properly visible once photographed the bird was easily distinguished.

Fig. 2: Flock of Bar-Headed Goose (*Anser indicus*) in the Hadinaru lake

Fig. 3: Dispersal of Flock of Bar-Headed Goose (*Anser indicus*) in the Hadinaru lake

After photographing the birds, with a speculation of it being a rare white fronted goose we went back to (Grimmett et al., 2016) to compare the species characteristics (Fig. 3), and indeed it was the Greater White-fronted Goose *Anser albifrons*. The lone *A. albifrons* was seen foraging and playing with Bar-headed goose. The bird was again seen and photographed 23rd Feb 2023, with word of mouth the bird was seen and photographed in the same lake premises by several other birdwatchers and nature enthusiasts (Table 1). Adults are mostly brown with white feathering around the base of a pinkish-orange bill. Black barring marks the belly and the undertail is white. In flight a white "U" at the base of the tail is visible. At rest, a thin white line stretches across their sides.

Juveniles lack the belly banding and white feathering around the bill. Both juveniles and adults have orangish legs.

IV. CONCLUSION

The Greater White-fronted Goose appears to be a frequent winter visitor to the northern plains, from the Indus Valley to eastern Uttar Pradesh, with isolated reports beyond (Rasmussen and Anderton, 2012). Apparently, this stands to be third record of the bird from state of Karnataka, in both the earlier sightings a lone bird was observed sometime with flocks of Bar-Headed Goose (Gunjal, 2019; Shailesh, 2020). The present record also stands to be the farthest inland record of the bird in the Indian Subcontinent.

Table 1: Showing sighting details of Greater White Fronted Goose at different location in different year.

Year of Sighting	Location	Number of Individuals	Association
2019	Navaloor Kere, Dharawad	1	ND
2020	Racihur	1	Bar Headed Goose
2023	Hadinur Lake, Mysore	1	Bar Headed Goose

*ND: Not Defined

REFERENCES

- [1.] Grimmett, R., Inskipp, C., & Inskipp, T. (2016). *Birds of the Indian Subcontinent: India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh and the Maldives*. Bloomsbury Publishing. <https://books.google.co.in/books?id=HvY0DQAAQB-AJ>.
- [2.] Rasmussen, P. C., & Anderton, J. C. (2012). *Birds of South Asia: The Ripley Guide, Volumes 1 & 2. Smithsonian Institution & Lynx Edicion. Washington DC and Barcelona, 1072pp.*
- [3.] Gunjal, V. (2019, December 29). *EBird Checklist—29 Dec 2019—Navaloor Kere □□□□□□ □□□□—38 species*. Ebird. <https://ebird.org/checklist/S62798890>
- [4.] Shailesh, S. (2020, February 23). *EBird Checklist—23 Feb 2020—Karnataka, IN (16.261, 77.305)—11 species*. Ebird. <https://ebird.org/checklist/S65178393>.